

ON A PRODUCTION MODEL WITH STOCHASTIC DEMAND FOR DECAYING ITEMS WITH PARTIAL BACKLOGGING

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Abstract: A production model is developed for deteriorating items with stochastic demand and budget and shortages constraints. We have also considered stochastically imperfect production and production rate is taken to be decision variable. This model is derived for single period and multi-items with non-linear holding cost and variable deterioration rate. Shortages are allowed with partial backlogging. The density function of demand is taken as linear for calculating the expected profit function. Numerical examples are also illustrated.

1. INTRODUCTION

Production inventory system is the most important aspect of a company as it corresponds to controlling an immediate change in demand. In the past decade, some researchers have considered constant, stock dependent demand and time dependent demand rate but in real situation, there are many commodities whose demand is not certain i.e. uncertainty or stochastic demand. Market forces acting to determine demand may be price, modern technology, existence of substitute and competitive products and seasonality etc. These forces are uncontrollable and independent in order to achieve the alternative objective of business which is profit maximization and cost minimization. Stochastic demand in inventory models has been extensively studied by many researchers.

In 1998, Eynan A., and Kropp D. H., considered a periodic review and joint replenishment in stochastic demand environments. Santosh Kumar U., and Pakkala T. P. M., (2001) discussed a continuous review (s, S) inventory system with stochastic demand for deteriorating item and the replenishment quantity is assumed to be random. Sana S., (2003) presents a stochastic EOQ model both for discrete and continuous distribution of demands of multi item products. Rao K. S., *et al.*, (2005) developed a stochastic order level inventory model for deteriorating items with inventory returns and special sales. Panda D., *et al.*, (2008) considered a mathematical model for a single period multi product manufacturing system producing stochastically imperfect items for stochastic demand under different types (Stochastic/Possibilistic/Necessity) of budgetary and limited shortages constraints.

In this model, a single period multi-items manufacturing system is considered for deteriorating items and imperfect production process with volume flexibility. Deterioration

rate is taken as variable. The total demand for a cycle is considered as stochastic. The rate of defective units is also stochastic. Shortages are allowed with partial backlogging. The backlogging rate is considered to be exponential decreasing function of time. Non-linear holding cost is taken into account. Profit maximization technique and numerical example are also used in this study.

2. FUNDAMENTAL ASSUMPTIONS AND NOTATIONS

2.1 Assumptions

1. This is a single period inventory model.
2. The inventory system is an imperfect production system and involves multiple items.
3. The unit production cost is a function of the rate of production.
4. The rate of production is considered to be a decision variable.
5. Percentage of imperfectness is stochastic.
6. Total demand over the period of cycle is stochastic and uniform over time.
7. Shortages are permitted and partially backlogged.
8. Deterioration rate is variable.
9. Non-linear holding cost function of time is also considered.
10. Screening costs for all items are same.

2.1 Notations

The inventory system involves n items and for i^{th} items ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$) are used:

1. A_i 's, B_i 's and R_i 's are constants in the density function $f_i(x_i)$.

$$f_i(x_i) = A_i + B_i x_i, \quad 0 \leq x_i \leq R_i$$

$$= 0, \quad \text{elsewhere}$$

2. $g_i(e_i) = d_i, \quad 0 \leq e_i \leq b_i$
- $= 0, \quad \text{elsewhere}$

where b_i 's and d_i 's are constants.

3. $C_{1i} t^{\theta}$ is variable holding cost per unit item per unit time.
4. $\theta_i t$ is variable deterioration rate.
5. C_{pi} is production cost per unit.

6. C_{si} is shortage cost per unit item.
7. e_i is rate of imperfect units.
8. C_{Lsi} is lost sale cost per unit item.
9. EAP ($Q_1, Q_2, \dots, Q_n$) is total expected average profit.
10. EP_i is the expected profit for i^{th} item.
11. $f_i(x_i)$ is probability density function of the demand x_i ($0 < x_i < \infty$).
12. $g_i(e_i)$ is probability density function for the rate of defective units e_i .
13. K_i is selling price per unit item of imperfect quality.
14. L_i is salvage value per unit.
15. P_i is production rate per unit time.
16. P_{ii} is production rate of perfect units which satisfies the relation $P_{ii} = (1 - e_i) P_i$.
17. $q_i(t)$ is on hand inventory at time $t \geq 0$.
18. Q_i is total production.
19. Q_{ii} is total production of good units which satisfies the relation $Q_{ii} = (1 - e_i) Q_i$.
20. Q_{si} is the shortage amount.
21. S_c is screening cost per unit item.
22. S_i is selling price per unit item of good quality.
23. S_M is maximum shortage cost allowed which is considered as stochastic.
24. t_{1i} is the production time.
25. t_{2i} is the time after which shortages occur.
26. T_i is fixed duration of the cycle.
27. x_i is total demand over time period $(0, T_i)$ which is stochastic.
28. B are maximum budget (total production cost and screening cost) which are considered as stochastic.
29. $B_r = e^{-\delta t}$ = Backlogging rate.
30. $C_{\theta i}$ is the deterioration cost.
31. The unit production cost is given by, $C_{P_i} = N + \frac{G}{Q_i} + HQ_i$ where N, G, H are all positive constants. This cost function is based on material cost, labor and energy costs and tool or die costs.

3. MODELING AND ANALYSIS

Case I: When shortages don't occur:

At time $t = 0$, the amount of stock is zero and production starts in this time and production stops at $t = t_{1i}$. And stock gets a level S .

$$\frac{dq_{1i}(t)}{dt} + \theta_i t q_{1i}(t) = (1 - e_i) P_i - \frac{x_i}{T_i} \quad 0 \leq t \leq t_{1i} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{dq_{2i}(t)}{dt} + \theta_i t q_{2i}(t) = -\frac{x_i}{T_i} \quad t_{1i} \leq t \leq T_i \quad (2)$$

With boundary conditions $q_i(0) = 0$, $q_i(T_i) = 0$,

Solutions of equations (1) & (2) are:

$$q_{1i}(t) = \left(P_{ii} - \frac{x_i}{T_i} \right) \left(t + \frac{\theta_i t^3}{6} \right) e^{-\frac{\theta_i t^2}{2}} \quad 0 \leq t \leq t_{1i} \quad (3)$$

$$q_{2i}(t) = \left[P_{ii} \left(t_{1i} + \frac{\theta_i t_{1i}^3}{6} \right) - \frac{x_i}{T_i} \left(t + \frac{\theta_i t^3}{6} \right) \right] e^{-\frac{\theta_i t^2}{2}} \quad t_{1i} \leq t \leq T_i \quad (4)$$

Where $P_{ii} = (1 - e_i) P_i$

Since shortages don't occur, $q_i(T_i) \geq 0$

$$\left[P_{ii} \left(t_{1i} + \frac{\theta_i t_{1i}^3}{6} \right) - \frac{x_i}{T_i} \left(t + \frac{\theta_i T_i^3}{6} \right) \right] \geq 0 \quad (\text{Neglecting the higher power of } t_{1i} \text{ \& } T_i)$$

$$x_i \leq P_{ii} t_{1i} \quad (5)$$

Now by notations, $Q_i = P_i t_{1i}$, $Q_{ii} = P_{ii} t_{1i}$

Expected holding cost for non-defective units of i^{th} item is given by,

$$\begin{aligned} &= C_{1i} \int_0^1 \left[\int_0^{Q_{ii}} \left\{ \int_0^{t_{1i}} t^\gamma q_{1i}(t) dt + \int_{t_{1i}}^{T_i} t^\gamma q_{2i}(t) dt \right\} f_i(x_i) dx_i \right] g_i(e_i) de_i \\ &= C_{1i} \int_0^1 \left[\int_0^{Q_{ii}} \left\{ \frac{Q_{ii} T_i^{\gamma+1}}{(\gamma+1)} - \frac{Q_{ii} x_i^{\gamma+1}}{(\gamma+1)(\gamma+2) P_{ii}^{\gamma+1}} + \frac{Q_{ii} x_i^2 \theta_i T_i^{\gamma+1}}{6(\gamma+1) P_{ii}^2} - \frac{Q_{ii} \theta_i x_i^{\gamma+3}}{3(\gamma+1)(\gamma+3)(\gamma+4) P_{ii}^{\gamma+3}} \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. - \frac{x_i T_i^{\gamma+1}}{(\gamma+2)} + \frac{x_i \theta_i T_i^{\gamma+3}}{3(\gamma+4)} - \frac{Q_{ii} \theta_i T_i^{\gamma+3}}{2(\gamma+3)} \right\} f_i(x_i) dx_i \right] g_i(e_i) de_i \quad (6) \end{aligned}$$

Expected holding cost for defective units of i^{th} item is given by,

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= C_{1i} \int_0^1 \left[\int_0^{t_i} e_i P_i t^{\gamma+1} dt \right] g_i(e_i) de_i \\
 &= C_{1i} \int_0^1 \left[\frac{e_i Q_i^{\gamma+2}}{(\gamma+2) P_i^{\gamma+1}} \right] g_i(e_i) de_i \tag{7}
 \end{aligned}$$

Expected deterioration cost for non-defective units of i^{th} item is given by,

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \int_0^1 \left[\int_0^{Q_i} \left\{ \int_0^{t_i} \theta_i t q_{1i}(t) dt + \int_{t_i}^{T_i} \theta_i t q_{2i}(t) dt \right\} f_i(x_i) dx_i \right] g_i(e_i) de_i \\
 &= \int_0^1 \left[\int_0^{Q_i} \left\{ \frac{Q_i \theta_i T_i^2}{2} - \frac{Q_i \theta_i x_i^2}{6 P_i^2} - \frac{\theta_i x_i T_i^2}{3} \right\} f_i(x_i) dx_i \right] g_i(e_i) de_i \tag{8}
 \end{aligned}$$

The salvage value is given by,

$$= L_i \int_0^1 \left[\int_0^{Q_i} (Q_i - x_i) f_i(x_i) dx_i \right] g_i(e_i) de_i \tag{9}$$

Total production cost of i^{th} item is given by,

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \left(N + \frac{G}{Q_i} + H Q_i \right) Q_i t_{1i} \\
 &= (N Q_i + G + H Q_i^2) \frac{x_i}{P_i} \tag{10}
 \end{aligned}$$

Case II: When shortages occur:

At time $t = 0$, the amount of stock is zero, and production starts in this time and production stops at $t = t_{1i}$. At $t = t_{1i}$, stock gets a level S . During (t_1, t_2) , the inventory level decreases mainly to meet up to demand and partly for deterioration. The stock reaches zero level at $t = t_{2i}$. Now shortages occur at $t = t_{3i}$, accumulate to the level R . Again at $t = t_{3i}$, production starts and the backlog is cleared at $t = T_i$. The cycle then repeats itself after the scheduling period T_i .

$$\frac{dq_{1i}(t)}{dt} + \theta_i t q_{1i}(t) = (1 - e_i) P_i - \frac{x_i}{T_i} \quad 0 \leq t \leq t_{1i} \tag{11}$$

$$\frac{dq_{2i}(t)}{dt} + \theta_i t q_{2i}(t) = -\frac{x_i}{T_i} \quad t_{1i} \leq t \leq t_{2i} \quad (12)$$

$$\frac{dq_{3i}(t)}{dt} = -e^{-\delta t} \frac{x_i}{T_i} \quad t_{2i} \leq t \leq t_{3i} \quad (13)$$

$$\frac{dq_{4i}(t)}{dt} = P_{ii} - \frac{x_i}{T_i} \quad t_{3i} \leq t \leq T_i \quad (14)$$

With boundary conditions

Solutions of equations (11), (12), (13) & (14) are:

$$q_{1i}(t) = \left(P_{ii} - \frac{x_i}{T_i} \right) \left(t + \frac{\theta_i t^3}{6} \right) e^{-\frac{\theta_i t^2}{2}} \quad 0 \leq t \leq t_{1i} \quad (15)$$

$$q_{2i}(t) = \left[P_{ii} \left(t_{1i} + \frac{\theta_i t_{1i}^3}{6} \right) - \frac{x_i}{T_i} \left(t + \frac{\theta_i t^3}{6} \right) \right] e^{-\frac{\theta_i t^2}{2}} \quad t_{1i} \leq t \leq t_{2i} \quad (16)$$

$$q_{3i}(t) = \frac{x_i}{\delta T_i} (e^{-\delta t} - e^{-\delta t_{2i}}) \quad t_{2i} \leq t \leq t_{3i} \quad (17)$$

$$q_{4i}(t) = \left(P_{ii} - \frac{x_i}{T_i} \right) (t - T_i) \quad t_{3i} \leq t \leq T_i \quad (18)$$

With the help of equation (17) & (18), we get:

$$\begin{aligned} t_{3i} &= \frac{x_i t_{2i}}{P_{ii} T_i} + T_i - \frac{x_i}{P_{ii}} \\ t_{3i} &= \frac{\theta_i t_{2i}}{P_i T_i} + T_i - \frac{Q_i}{P_i} \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

Expected holding cost for non-defective units of i^{th} item is given by,

$$\begin{aligned} &= C_{1i} \int_0^1 \left[\int_{Q_{ii}}^{\infty} \left\{ \int_0^{t_{1i}} t^\gamma q_{1i}(t) dt + \int_{t_{1i}}^{t_{2i}} t^\gamma q_{2i}(t) dt \right\} f_i(x_i) dx_i \right] g_i(e_i) de_i \\ &= C_{1i} \int_0^1 \left[\int_{Q_{ii}}^{\infty} \left\{ \frac{Q_{ii} t_i^{\gamma+1}}{(\gamma+1)} - \frac{Q_{ii} x_i^{\gamma+1}}{(\gamma+1)(\gamma+2)P_{ii}^{\gamma+1}} + \frac{Q_{ii} x_i^2 \theta_i t_{2i}^{\gamma+1}}{6(\gamma+1)P_{ii}^2} - \frac{Q_{ii} \theta_i x_i^{\gamma+3}}{3(\gamma+1)(\gamma+3)(\gamma+4)P_{ii}^{\gamma+3}} \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. - \frac{x_i t_i^{\gamma+1}}{(\gamma+2)T_i} + \frac{x_i \theta_i t_{2i}^{\gamma+4}}{3(\gamma+4)T_i} - \frac{Q_{ii} \theta_i t_{2i}^{\gamma+3}}{2(\gamma+3)} \right\} f_i(x_i) dx_i \right] g_i(e_i) de_i \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

Expected deterioration cost for non-defective units of i^{th} item is given by,

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \int_0^1 \left[\int_{Q_{ii}}^{\infty} \left\{ \int_0^{t_{1i}} \theta_i t q_{1i}(t) dt + \int_{t_{1i}}^{t_{2i}} \theta_i t q_{2i}(t) dt \right\} f_i(x_i) dx_i \right] g_i(e_i) de_i \\
 &= \int_0^1 \left[\int_{Q_{ii}}^{\infty} \left\{ \frac{Q_{ii} \theta_i t_{2i}^2}{2} - \frac{Q_{ii} \theta_i x_i^2}{6P_{ii}^2} - \frac{\theta_i x_i t_{2i}^2}{3T_i} \right\} f_i(x_i) dx_i \right] g_i(e_i) de_i \tag{21}
 \end{aligned}$$

Expected shortages cost for i^{th} item = $C_{Si} Q_{Si}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= C_{Si} \int_0^1 \left[\int_{Q_{ii}}^{\infty} \left\{ \int_{t_{2i}}^{t_{3i}} (-q_{3i}(t)) dt + \int_{t_{3i}}^{T_i} (-q_{4i}(t)) dt \right\} f_i(x_i) dx_i \right] g_i(e_i) de_i \\
 &= C_{Si} \int_0^1 \left[\int_{Q_{ii}}^{\infty} \left\{ \frac{x_i t_{2i}}{\delta T_i} - \frac{x_i^2 t_{2i}}{\delta P_{ii} T_i^2} - \frac{x_i}{\delta} + \frac{x_i^2}{\delta P_{ii} T_i} - \frac{x_i t_{2i} e^{-\delta t_{2i}}}{\delta T_i} + \frac{x_i^2 t_{2i} e^{-\delta t_{2i}}}{\delta P_{ii} T_i^2} + \frac{x_i e^{-\delta t_{2i}}}{\delta} \right. \right. \\
 &\quad \left. \left. - \frac{x_i^2 t_{2i} e^{-\delta t_{2i}}}{\delta P_{ii} T_i} + \frac{1}{2} \left(P_{ii} - \frac{x_i}{T_i} \right) \left(\frac{x_i^2}{P_{ii}^2} + \frac{x_i^2 t_{2i}^2}{P_{ii}^2 T_i^2} - \frac{2x_i^2 t_{2i}}{P_{ii}^2 T_i} \right) \right\} f_i(x_i) dx_i \right] g_i(e_i) de_i \tag{22}
 \end{aligned}$$

Where,

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= Q_{Si} \int_0^1 \left[\int_{Q_{ii}}^{\infty} \left\{ \frac{x_i t_{2i}}{\delta T_i} - \frac{x_i^2 t_{2i}}{\delta P_{ii} T_i^2} - \frac{x_i}{\delta} + \frac{x_i^2}{\delta P_{ii} T_i} - \frac{x_i t_{2i} e^{-\delta t_{2i}}}{\delta T_i} + \frac{x_i^2 t_{2i} e^{-\delta t_{2i}}}{\delta P_{ii} T_i^2} + \frac{x_i e^{-\delta t_{2i}}}{\delta} \right. \right. \\
 &\quad \left. \left. - \frac{x_i^2 t_{2i} e^{-\delta t_{2i}}}{\delta P_{ii} T_i} + \frac{1}{2} \left(P_{ii} - \frac{x_i}{T_i} \right) \left(\frac{x_i^2}{P_{ii}^2} + \frac{x_i^2 t_{2i}^2}{P_{ii}^2 T_i^2} - \frac{2x_i^2 t_{2i}}{P_{ii}^2 T_i} \right) \right\} f_i(x_i) dx_i \right] g_i(e_i) de_i \tag{23}
 \end{aligned}$$

Expected shortages cost for i^{th} item is given by,

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= C_{LSi} \int_0^1 \left[\int_{Q_{ii}}^{\infty} \left\{ \int_{t_{2i}}^{t_{3i}} (1 - e^{-\delta t}) \frac{x_i}{T_i} dt \right\} f_i(x_i) dx_i \right] g_i(e_i) de_i \\
 &= C_{LSi} \int_0^1 \left[\int_{Q_{ii}}^{\infty} \frac{x_i \delta}{2T_{ii}} \left\{ \frac{x_i^2 t_{2i}^2}{P_{ii}^2 T_i^2} + T_i^2 + \frac{x_i^2}{P_{ii}^2} + \frac{2x_i t_{2i}}{P_{ii}} - \frac{2x_i T_i}{P_{ii}} - \frac{2x_i^2 t_{2i}}{P_{ii}^2 T_i} - t_{2i}^2 \right\} f_i(x_i) dx_i \right] g_i(e_i) de_i \tag{24}
 \end{aligned}$$

Total production cost of i^{th} item is given by,

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \left(N + \frac{G}{Q_i} + HQ_i \right) Q_i (T_i + t_{1i} - t_{3i}) \\
 &= (NQ_i + G + HQ_i^2) \left(\frac{2x_i}{P_{ii}} - \frac{x_i t_{2i}}{P_{ii} T_i} \right) \tag{25}
 \end{aligned}$$

We have to maximize the expected average profit subject to probabilistic imprecise limitations on total production cost along with screening cost under budget and shortage constraints and this is given by,

$$\text{Max. } EAP(Q_1, Q_2 \dots Q_n)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \sum_{i=1}^n (C_{P_i} + S_c) Q_i \leq B \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_{i=1}^n C_{S_i} Q_{S_i} \leq S_M \quad (26)$$

$$\text{Expected profit for } i^{\text{th}} \text{ item} = EP_i$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \text{Revenue from sale of perfect units} + \text{Salvage value} \\ &+ \text{revenue from sale of imperfect units} - \text{holding cost} \\ &\text{for non-defective units} - \text{holding cost for defective} \\ &\text{units} - \text{deterioration cost-shortages cost-lost sale} \\ &\text{cost-screening cost-production cost} \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

Hence for the entire items total expected average profit is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} EAP(Q_1, Q_2 \dots Q_n) &= \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{T_i} EP_i \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{T_i} \left[S_i \int_0^1 \left\{ \int_0^{Q_{ii}} x_i f_i(x_i) dx_i + Q_{ii} \int_{Q_{ii}}^{\infty} f_i(x_i) dx_i \right\} g_i(e_i) de_i \right. \\ &+ L_i \int_0^1 \left[\int_0^{Q_{ii}} (Q_{ii} - x_i) f_i(x_i) dx_i \right] g_i(e_i) de_i + K_i Q_i \int_0^1 e_i g_i(e_i) de_i \\ &- C_{1i} \int_0^1 \left[\int_0^{Q_{ii}} \left\{ \frac{Q_{ii} T_i^{\gamma+1}}{(\gamma+1)} - \frac{Q_{ii} x_i^{\gamma+1}}{(\gamma+1)(\gamma+2) P_{ii}^{\gamma+1}} + \frac{Q_{ii} x_i^2 \theta_i T_i^{\gamma+1}}{6(\gamma+1) P_{ii}^2} \right. \right. \\ &- \frac{Q_{ii} \theta_i x_i^{\gamma+3}}{3(\gamma+1)(\gamma+3)(\gamma+4) P_{ii}^{\gamma+3}} - \frac{x_i T_i^{\gamma+1}}{(\gamma+2)} + \frac{x_i \theta_i T_i^{\gamma+3}}{3(\gamma+4)} \\ &\left. \left. - \frac{Q_{ii} \theta_i T_i^{\gamma+3}}{2(\gamma+3)} \right\} f_i(x_i) dx_i \right] g_i(e_i) de_i - C_{1i} \int_0^1 \left[\frac{e_i Q_i^{\gamma+2}}{(\gamma+2) P_i^{\gamma+1}} \right] g_i(e_i) de_i \\ &- C_{1i} \int_0^1 \left[\int_{Q_{ii}}^{\infty} \left\{ \frac{Q_{ii} t_{2i}^{\gamma+1}}{(\gamma+1)} - \frac{Q_{ii} x_i^{\gamma+1}}{(\gamma+1)(\gamma+2) P_{ii}^{\gamma+1}} + \frac{Q_{ii} x_i^2 \theta_i t_{2i}^{\gamma+1}}{6(\gamma+1) P_{ii}^2} \right. \right. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & -\frac{Q_{ii}\theta_i x_i^{\gamma+3}}{3(\gamma+1)(\gamma+3)(\gamma+4)P_{ii}^{\gamma+3}} - \frac{x_i t_{2i}^{\gamma+1}}{(\gamma+2)T_i} + \frac{x_i \theta_i t_{2i}^{\gamma+4}}{3(\gamma+4)T_i} \\
 & - \left. \frac{Q_{ii}\theta_i t_{2i}^{\gamma+3}}{2(\gamma+3)} \right\} f_i(x_i) dx_i \Big] g_i(e_i) de_i - \int_0^1 \left[\int_0^{Q_{ii}} \left\{ \frac{Q_{ii}\theta_i T_i^2}{2} - \frac{Q_{ii}\theta_i x_i^2}{6P_{ii}^2} \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. - \frac{\theta_i x_i T_i^2}{3} \right\} f_i(x_i) dx_i \right] g_i(e_i) de_i - \int_0^1 \left[\int_{Q_{ii}}^\infty \left\{ \frac{Q_{ii}\theta_i t_{2i}^2}{2} - \frac{Q_{ii}\theta_i x_i^2}{6P_{ii}^2} \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. - \frac{\theta_i x_i t_{2i}^2}{3T_i} \right\} f_i(x_i) dx_i \right] g_i(e_i) de_i - C_{Si} \int_0^1 \left[\int_{Q_{ii}}^\infty \left\{ \frac{x_i t_{2i}}{\delta T_i} - \frac{x_i^2 t_{2i}}{\delta P_{ii} T_i^2} \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. - \frac{x_i}{\delta} + \frac{x_i^2}{\delta P_{ii} T_i} - \frac{x_i t_{2i} e^{-\delta t_{2i}}}{\delta T_i} + \frac{x_i^2 t_{2i} e^{-\delta t_{2i}}}{\delta P_{ii} T_i^2} + \frac{x_i e^{-\delta t_{2i}}}{\delta} - \frac{x_i^2 t_{2i} e^{-\delta t_{2i}}}{\delta P_{ii} T_i} \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. + \frac{1}{2} \left(P_{ii} - \frac{x_i}{T_i} \right) \left(\frac{x_i^2}{P_{ii}^2} + \frac{x_i^2 t_{2i}^2}{P_{ii}^2 T_i^2} - \frac{2x_i^2 t_{2i}}{P_{ii}^2 T_i} \right) \right\} f_i(x_i) dx_i \right] g_i(e_i) de_i \\
 & - C_{LSi} \int_0^1 \left[\int_{Q_{ii}}^\infty \frac{x_{ii} \delta}{2T_{ii}} \left\{ \frac{x_i^2 t_{2i}^2}{P_{ii}^2 T_i^2} + T_i^2 + \frac{x_i^2}{P_{ii}^2} + \frac{2x_i t_{2i}}{P_{ii}} - \frac{2x_i T_i}{P_{ii}} \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. - \frac{2x_i^2 t_{2i}}{P_{ii}^2 T_i} - t_{2i}^2 \right\} f_i(x_i) dx_i \right] g_i(e_i) de_i - S_c Q_i - (NQ_i + FG + HQ_i^2) \frac{x_i}{P_{ii}} \\
 & - (NQ_i + G + HQ_i^2) \left(\frac{2x_i}{P_{ii}} - \frac{x_i t_{2i}}{P_{ii} T_i} \right) \Big] \tag{28}
 \end{aligned}$$

4. NUMERICAL ILLUSTRATION

The above model is illustrated numerically.

Common input parameters are:

$$S_c = 0.45, \delta = 0.04, \gamma = 0.5, G = 2500, H = 0.01, N = 150$$

Table 1

Item	A_i	B_i	b_i	P_i	T_i	S_i	L_i	Q_i	d_i	R_i	θ_i	K_i	C_{Si}	C_{LSi}
I	0.035	0.0045	0.04	50	10	20	12	100	30	700	0.005	6	3	12
II	0.03	0.005	0.05	55	11	22	13	110	25	800	0.006	7	4	13

Table 2

$P_1 = 50, \theta_1 = .005, P_2 = 55$			$P_1 = 50, \theta_1 = .005, P_2 = 56$			$P_1 = 50, \theta_1 = .005, P_2 = 57$		
θ_2	t_{22}	EAP	θ_2	t_{22}	EAP	θ_2	T_{22}	EAP
0.004	6.3987	28945100000	0.004	6.4928	28953800000	0.004	6.5845	28962300000
0.005	5.8147	22666100000	0.005	5.9111	22673200000	0.005	6.0056	22680100000
0.006	5.3352	19245400000	0.006	5.4320	19251300000	0.006	5.5271	19257000000
0.007	4.9346	17177400000	0.007	5.0305	17182400000	0.007	5.1250	17187300000
0.008	4.5947	15832100000	0.008	4.6892	15836300000	0.008	4.7823	15840500000

Table 3

$P_1 = 50, \theta_2 = .006, P_2 = 55$			$P_1 = 51, \theta_2 = .006, P_2 = 55$			$P_1 = 50, \theta_2 = .006, P_2 = 55$		
θ_1	t_{21}	EAP	θ_1	t_{21}	EAP	θ_1	T_{21}	EAP
0.003	7.0871	39238000000	0.003	7.1665	39244700000	0.003	7.2431	39251200000
0.004	6.4745	25582800000	0.004	6.5625	25588100000	0.004	6.6476	25593400000
0.005	5.9649	19245400000	0.005	6.0579	19249900000	0.005	6.1482	19254200000
0.006	5.5346	15794500000	0.006	5.6301	15798300000	0.006	5.7233	15802000000
0.007	5.1663	13709100000	0.007	5.2629	13712400000	0.007	5.3574	13715500000

Figure 1

Figure 2

5. CONCLUSION

A volume flexible imperfect production model is developed for deteriorating items with stochastic demand. Shortages are permitted in inventory with partial backlogging. In this model, we are using a variable holding cost and the holding cost is regarded as a non-linear function of the length of time. This type of assumption is quite appropriate when the value of the unsold items decreases with time. Retailers in supermarket face this problem while selling products like green vegetables, fruits and breads whose quality drops with each passing day. As a result, increasing holding cost is incurred to arrange better spoilage and to maintain freshness of the items in stock. The functional form of non-linear time dependent holding cost is quite realistic from that part of view. Profit of the whole system is highly sensitivity towards the deterioration rate. It means as we increase the deterioration rate of the items then the profit decrease.

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